

used at a concentration of 100 ppm as a spreader. The treated pots were maintained at 30° in a green house. After four weeks the herbicidal activity of each compound against each weed and their phytotoxicity against crops were evaluated. The herbicidal rating score (from 0~5) was based on visual observation. Zero means no significant effect on seedling growth while 5 means seedling death.

Herbicidal activity data (not shown) indicate that all the test compounds have moderate to low activity towards weeds but quite safe towards crops. Although, various toxophoric groups and structures have been combined in the titled molecules with a hope of achieving compounds of better biocidal potency, the results are not very encouraging. This indicates that the activity of any compound may not necessarily be related to the numerical sum of all toxophores present in the molecule.

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Synthesis of some New Pyrazolinone Azo Dyes

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THE importance of pyrazolinones in the field of dyes is well-known¹. Almost all pyrazolinone dyes are azo dyes having an aryl azo group substituted at the 4-position of a 2-pyrazolin-5-one. A search

of the literature reveals that no work has been reported so far, on the pyrazolinones in which a naphthyl ring is present at the N¹ position. The present work was therefore undertaken to synthesise a number of pyrazolinone azo dyes with better dyeing characteristics. They have been prepared from the appropriate aryl hydrazones of ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate and their subsequent cyclo-condensation with N-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide. The pyrazolinones have also been examined for their dyeing characteristics on wool, cotton and polyester using two different mordants, namely chromium sulphate and copper sulphate.

Experimental

The precursors, aryl hydrazones of ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate² and N-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide³ were prepared by the reported method.

The condensation of substituted aryl hydrazones with N-2-naphthyl malonamic acid hydrazide was brought about by refluxing an equimolecular mixture of the alcoholic solution of the reactants in the presence of few drops of glacial acetic acid for 0.5–3 h. The resulting brightly coloured products were purified by washing repeatedly with hot ethanol. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel G plates in 10% methanol-benzene.

Condensation of N-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide with ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate-2-(2-methyl)-phenylhydrazone. Formation of 4-(2-methyl)phenylhydrazono-N¹-2-naphthylaminomalonyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one: A mixture of ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate-2-(2-methyl)phenylhydrazone (1 g, 1 mol) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) and an ethanolic solution of N-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide (0.96 g, 1 mol) was refluxed for 45 min in the presence of glacial acetic acid (4–5 drops). The resulting yellow solid was purified by washing several times with ethanol. It was identified as 4-(2-methyl)phenylhydrazono-N¹-2-naphthylamino malonyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.72 g, 42.15%), m.p. 220° (Found: C, 67.50; H, 5.07; N, 11.29. C₂₄H₂₁N₃O₃ requires: C, 67.44; H, 4.91; N, 11.24%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 200 (NH), 3 050 (aromatic-CH stretching 2-naphthalene ring), 1 735 (CONH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N), 1 560 (-NH-N=) and 1 360 cm⁻¹ (CH₃ bending).

Similarly other 4-(substituted)phenyl hydrazone-N¹-2-naphthylaminomalonyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones were prepared.

Condensation of N-2-naphthylmalonamic acid hydrazide with ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate-2-(4-bromo)-phenylhydrazone. Formation of 4-(4-bromo)phenylhydrazono-N¹-2-naphthylaminomalonyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one: Following the above procedure a dull green solid was obtained (0.12 g, 12.19%), m.p. 220° (Found: N, 14.35. C₂₃H₁₇BrN₃O₃ requires: N, 14.22%). The δ (CDCl₃) 1.55 (3H, CH₃C=N), 4.20 (2H, COCH₂CO), 7.34–7.39 (2H, aromatic and in the vicinity of Br), 7.4–7.5 (4H, aromatic at

positions 5, 6, 7, 8 of 2-naphthalene ring), 7.55–7.6 (2H, aromatic and in the vicinity of NHN), 7.75 (1H, aromatic and at position-4 of 2-naphthalene ring), 7.80–7.85 (2H, aromatic and at positions 1 and 3 of the 2-naphthalene ring), 8.29 (1H, NHN), and 9.25 (1H, CONH).

The physical data of the pyrazolones are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE PYRAZOLINONES*

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2-CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₃	220	42.15
2.	4-CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₃	249	37.47
3.	2-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	245	26.94
4.	4-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClN ₂ O ₃	230	33.48
5.	4-Br	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ BrN ₂ O ₃	220	12.19
6.	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄	202	33.86
7.	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄	224	25.58
8.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄	237	33.91
9.	4-NO ₂	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃	227	26.92

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The pyrazolinones were examined for their dyeing characteristics on wool, cotton and polyester using two different mordants, namely chromium sulphate (for wool) and copper sulphate (for cotton and polyester). The pyrazolinones imparted beautiful shades of light yellow to orange on these fibres. Investigations showed that the colours produced are fast to light and soap.

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Fragrant Volatiles in Rice and Marking Fluid of Tiger

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THE marking fluid (MF) of the tiger ejected upwards through the urinary channel but distinct from urine, is believed to be the source of semiochemicals, i.e. pheromones, which serve to mark territory and to invite the opposite sex¹⁻⁴.

The study of the chemical nature of the volatiles in the MF, the likely candidates for pheromones, was initiated earlier^{2,3}. This is associated with the science of smell, a formidable subject for the chemists, because a very few molecules, sometimes a single one, can be perceived by an animal. Since 1986 we have been studying such molecules of smell in the MF of several adult tigers and in the urine of two cub tigers at Nandan Kanan open-air zoo, Orissa. The MF from adult tigers was collected by a procedure developed over the last ten years, based on certain behavioural properties of tigers. MF has a characteristic pleasant aroma, partly masked by ammonia and other constituents. The adult urine, but not the urine of the cub, contains the same aroma. Under the best conditions this aroma is surprisingly close to the fragrant Indian rice varieties. Only 8% of fragrance in cooked rice has recently been elucidated to be 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline⁵ and the major part of aroma of cooked and uncooked rice is still unknown.

The fragrant material could be extracted from MF by chloroform, diethyl ether, hexane or heptane. When these extracts or the steam distillate of MF were shaken with 1 N HCl, the aroma disappeared. When these aqueous acid extracts were rendered alkaline with 1 N NaOH solution, the aroma reappeared (The rice aroma also exhibited these very properties). This behaviour of the fragrant material from the tiger suggested that it might be an organic base, rather like the rice aroma.

We have therefore carried out a comparative study of the retention-characteristics of these two compounds in both paper chromatography (pc) and gas-liquid chromatography (glc) in order to find out whether these molecules are identical from the stand-point of retention characteristics.

Following our earlier work^{2,3}, a thorough search was made to isolate the aroma-substance with the help of pc. Acidified steam-distillate or the supernatant after centrifugation of acidified MF was spotted on Whatman 3M paper strips and developed up to ~17 cm with a solvent mixture of n-butanol,